

1 **Comparative metabolomic study of transgenic versus conventional**
2 **soybean using capillary electrophoresis-time- of- flight mass**
3 **spectrometry**

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17

18 **Abstract**

19

20 In this work, capillary electrophoresis - time-of-flight mass spectrometry (CE-
21 TOF-MS) is proposed to identify and quantify the main metabolites found in transgenic
22 soybean and its corresponding non-transgenic parental line both grown under identical
23 conditions. The procedure includes optimization of metabolites extraction, separation by
24 CE, on-line electrospray-TOF-MS analysis and data evaluation. A large number of
25 extraction procedures and background electrolytes are tested in order to obtain a highly
26 reproducible and sensitive analytical methodology. Using this approach, a large number
27 of metabolites was tentatively identified based on the high mass accuracy provided by
28 TOF-MS analyzer, together with the isotopic pattern and expected electrophoretic
29 mobility of these compounds. In general, the same metabolites and in similar amounts
30 were found in the conventional and transgenic variety. However, significant differences
31 were also observed in some specific cases when the conventional variety was
32 compared with its corresponding transgenic line. The selection of these metabolites as
33 possible biomarkers of transgenic soybean is discussed, although a larger number of
34 samples needs to be analyzed in order to validate this point. It is concluded that
35 metabolomic procedures based on CE-MS can open new perspectives in the study of
36 transgenic foods in order to corroborate (or not) the equivalence with their conventional
37 counterparts.

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39 **Keywords:** Soybean; Metabolites; Genetically modified organisms (GMOs); Capillary
40 electrophoresis; Time of flight.

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1. Introduction

Genetic engineering has been applied to plants since the mid-1980s and since then the use of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) has seen a great increase in agriculture and food science [1]. As an example, in 2005 more than 900.000 km² of GM crops were cultivated worldwide. GM plants are obtained by inserting manipulated fragments of DNA from a different organism in order to improve some characteristic of the original crop, such as its resistance to plagues, pesticides or extreme environmental conditions, to provide better nutritional properties, etc [2, 3].

The transgenic soybean variety tolerant to glyphosate is one of the most extended GM crops in the world. In 2005, 87% of U.S. soybean fields were planted with glyphosate resistant varieties [4]. Glyphosate binds to and blocks the activity of 5-enolpyruvylshikimate-3-phosphate synthase (EPSPS), an enzyme of the aromatic amino acid biosynthetic pathway (shikimate pathway) [5]. The glyphosate inhibition of EPSPS prevents the plant from producing the aromatic amino acids (phenylalanine, tyrosine, tryptophan) essential for protein synthesis. Some microorganisms have a version of 5-enolpyruvylshikimate-3-phosphate synthetase that is resistant to glyphosate inhibition. The version used in genetically modified crops was isolated from *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain CP4 (CP4 EPSPS) that was resistant to glyphosate [6, 7]. This CP4 EPSPS gene was cloned and transfected into soybeans, and in 1996, such genetically modified soybean was made commercially available. This greatly improved the ability to control weeds in soybean fields since glyphosate could be sprayed on fields without affecting the crop.

In the last decades, several aspects of GMOs have been criticized and scientific and public debate is open about their influence on the environment and their safety as food and feed. As a result, many countries have implemented regulations regarding the development, growing, and commercialization of these genetically modified products. The European Union (EU) has dedicated special attention to customer information, and food products containing more than 0.9% of genetically modified soybean and/or maize must be labelled as transgenic [8].

Therefore, the development of fast, sensitive and informative analytical methods is of paramount importance not only to fulfil the labelling requirements but also to evaluate other possible alterations in GM grains and foods [9]. In this regard, there are two general approaches for the detection of GMOs, based on the detection of two types of macromolecules specific for the genetic modification: proteins and DNA. The new or modified proteins contained in novel foods and ingredients are mainly detected using immunoassay methods (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) methods). However, protein detection by immunoassay requires the use of antibodies raised against the protein encoded by the transgene [10,11]. Capillary electrophoresis (CE) [12, 13] and 2D electrophoresis, where mixtures of proteins are separated by two properties, have also been used to study the different protein profiles between some transgenic and non transgenic crops [14-16].

Regarding the detection of GMOs based on DNA analysis, the most frequent procedure is to apply polymerase chain reaction (PCR) methods, where DNA fragments are amplified, followed by agarose gel electrophoresis plus ethidium bromide staining of the amplification products [17]. To avoid the restrictions in sensitivity and resolution of the slab gel electrophoresis, capillary gel electrophoresis (CGE) has been recently used as an attractive alternative providing very high efficiency, resolution and sensitivity [18,19]. DNA separations are performed in capillaries using polymer solutions where the electroosmotic flow (EOF) is completely suppressed [20-24]. Other

92 method like PCR and immunoassay kits (PCR-ELISA) has also been described in the
93 field of GMO analysis [25,26]. One of the last challenges in GMO detection is the
94 development of multiplex PCR approaches able to detect multiple GMOs in a single
95 analysis [27,28]. The separation and detection of multiplex-PCR products for the
96 detection of GMOs were achieved by agarose gel electrophoresis (AGE) [29] and other
97 innovative procedure like, capillary electrophoresis, microchip capillary electrophoresis
98 (MCE) [30], capillary gel electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescent detection
99 (CGE-LIF) [31,32], and DNA arrays or biosensors [33]. One of the main deficiencies of
100 the procedures based on DNA are related to the semiquantitative character of the PCR
101 amplification, recently overcome by the development of real-time PCR (RT-PCR)
102 [34,35] and competitive quantitative PCR (QC-PCR) techniques using capillary gel
103 electrophoresis [36,37].

104 An alternative procedure is to investigate the substantial equivalence of a GMO
105 and its isogenic counterpart using profiling (or shotgun) procedures. In this regard, the
106 comparison of the content of secondary metabolites has been proposed as an interesting
107 approach to carry out this type of comparative studies. In the case of soybean, the
108 studies done so far have been focused on the analysis of a given family of compounds
109 following a more targeted approach. Thus, isoflavones, the main secondary metabolites
110 in soybean, have been determined by HPLC [38] and LC/MS [39] and the results did
111 not show significant differences between GM and non-GM soybeans. In other
112 publication, the content of tocopherols, sterols, and phospholipids in oils obtained from
113 GM soybeans and non-GM soybeans were determined by normal- and reversed-phase
114 HPLC and GC observing some difference in the phospholipids fraction [40]. Several
115 methods for identifying secondary metabolites of soybean, mainly isoflavones, have
116 been published based on HPLC and capillary electrophoresis techniques with UV
117 [41,42] and mass spectrometry detection [43,44], however, these works were not
118 dealing with GM vs. non-GM comparisons.

119 The aim of this study was to develop a new analytical strategy based on
120 comparative metabolomics able to determine differences between GM soybean and its
121 isogenic wild variety both grown under the same conditions. The proposed method is
122 based on the following steps: i) soybean metabolites extraction, ii) CE separation, iii)
123 on-line ESI-TOF-MS analysis and iv) data evaluation.

124 125 **2. Experimental**

126 127 *2.1. Chemicals and samples.*

128
129 All chemicals were of analytical reagent grade and used as received. Ammonium
130 hydrogencarbonate from Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland) ammonium acetate from Panreac
131 (Barcelona, Spain) and ammonium hydroxide from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) were
132 used for the CE running buffers at different concentrations and pH values. Buffers were
133 prepared by weighting the quantity indicated in doubly distilled water and adding
134 ammonium hydroxide to adjust the pH. Water was deionized by using a Milli-Q-system
135 (Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA). Triethylamine (TEA) (Sigma, St. Louis, MO, USA)
136 and 2-propanol of HPLC grade (Scharlau, Barcelona, Spain) were used in the sheath
137 liquid. For the extraction of the soybean compounds, methanol, ethanol, hexane, and
138 acetonitrile from Lab-Scan (Dublin, Ireland) and ethyl acetate from Fluka (Buchs,
139 Switzerland) were used.

140 The soybean used for the optimisation was obtained from an herbalist's shop
141 (Madrid, Spain). The isogenic and transgenic soybean seeds used for the comparative

142 metabolomic study were supplied by Professor Giovanni Dinelli (University of
143 Bologna). Isogenic and transgenic plants were grown under the same conditions in a
144 growth chamber: at the end of growing cycle the seeds were collected and finely ground
145 as flour. The transgenic and nontransgenic nature of all these soybean samples was
146 confirmed based on their DNA using an analytical procedure developed in our
147 laboratory and described elsewhere [21, 23, 24, 32, 36].

148 149 2.2. *Extraction procedures.*

150
151 To extract the major number of compounds from the soybean seeds different
152 organic solvents together with different water percentages were tested: methanol (60,
153 80, 90 and 100% v/v), ethanol (60, 80, 90 and 100% v/v), ethyl acetate (100% v/v) and
154 acetonitrile (70 and 100% v/v). All the extracts profiles were compared using the same
155 initial CE-UV conditions: running buffer 100 mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH
156 9 + 5% v/v acetonitrile, voltage of 28 kV, 5 s injection time, and detection wavelength
157 at 200 nm. With these initial conditions the electric current was around 80 μ A.

158 The extraction protocol was as follows: soybean seeds were finely grounded at
159 5°C using a mill and maintained in the fridge at 4°C. After, 1 g of the milled samples
160 was mixed with 15 mL of the different solvents and extracted during 30 min in the
161 ultrasonic bath. The extracts were then centrifuged at 5750 g for 15 min at 5°C. The
162 supernatants were separated in three aliquots of 4 mL and evaporated in a concentrator.
163 The residue was dissolved in 500 μ L of the solvent and analysed by CE-UV. It is
164 important to keep the temperature below 20°C because it is known that this temperature
165 is the most suitable for extracting the compounds (specially isoflavones) from seeds
166 with little or no modifications of its composition [42].

167 An alternative extraction procedure was tested removing the fat (mainly
168 phospholipids) with hexane previously to the extraction. Thus, once the soybean was
169 milled, 1 g was extracted with 10 ml of hexane during 15 min in the ultrasonic bath. The
170 extracts were centrifuged at 5750 g for 10 min at 5 °C, the supernatant was eliminated
171 and the solid was extracted with the solvent as described above. The use of hexane did
172 not improve the results of the extraction.

173 174 2.3. *CE-UV and CE-MS.*

175
176 Analyses were performed in a PACE/2100 apparatus (Beckman, Fullerton, CA,
177 USA) equipped with a UV-vis detector working at 200 nm and coupled to a Bruker
178 Daltonik micrOTOF mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonik, Bremen, Germany) using an
179 orthogonal electrospray ionization (ESI) interface (model G1607A from Agilent
180 Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). The CE instrument was controlled by a personal
181 computer running the System Gold Software from Beckman. Bare fused-silica
182 capillaries with 50 μ m i.d. and 375 μ m o.d. were purchased from Composite Metal
183 Services (Worcester, England). The detection length to the UV detector was 84 cm and
184 the total length was 90 cm (corresponding to the MS detection length). Injections were
185 made at the anodic end using N₂ at pressure of 3570 Pa at the times indicated in each
186 case.

187 Electrical contact at the electrospray needle tip was established via a sheath
188 liquid pumped by a syringe pump (74900-00-05, Cole Palmer, Vernon Hills, IL, USA).
189 The ESI-voltage of the micrOTOF is applied at the end cap of the transfer capillary to
190 the MS (-4.2 kV) with the spray needle being grounded. The mass spectrometer was run
191 in the negative mode. The micrOTOF was operated to acquire spectra in the range of

192 50-1000 m/z. Transfer parameters were optimised for high sensitivity while keeping the
193 resolution to better 10000. The accurate mass data of the molecular ions were processed
194 by DataAnalysis 3.3. software (Bruker Daltonik). It provides a list of possible elemental
195 formulae by means of the Generate Molecular Formula editor (GMF), which uses a
196 CHNO algorithm. This provides information about elemental composition, sigma and
197 m/z values. The calibration of the MS was performed using sodium formiate.

198 All new capillaries were conditioned before their first use by rising for 30 min
199 with 0.1 M sodium hydroxide followed by water for 10 min and then running buffer for
200 20 min. Capillary conditioning between runs was carried out by flushing for 10 min
201 with 0.1 M sodium hydroxide, then for 5 min with water and finally for 10 min with
202 running buffer. At the end of the day the capillary was rinsed with water for 15 min and
203 dried with air for 5 min.

204 205 **3. Results and discussion**

206 207 *3.1. Optimization of metabolites extraction from soybean samples.*

208
209 The possibility to obtain a good extraction procedure of metabolites from
210 soybean was deeply explored. To do this, the different extraction procedures above
211 described were investigated in order to determine the extraction conditions that led to a
212 higher number of peaks in a reproducible way, assuming this would mean a higher
213 number of metabolites extracted. CE-UV was initially employed to monitorize at 200
214 nm the results of the extraction. The soybean bought in a local market was selected for
215 the extraction optimization. As the aim of this part was to extract the highest number of
216 possible metabolites, extraction solutions able to cover a wide range of polarities were
217 frequently used, including ethanol:water and methanol:water mixtures at different
218 concentrations. The results obtained using the different extraction solvents are given in
219 Fig 1. The best extraction procedures were obtained with methanol and ethanol with
220 different percentages of water. The intensity of some peaks decreased at both higher
221 (90% v/v) and smaller (60% v/v) percentages of organic solvent. Finally, the selected
222 extract solvent consist of methanol/water (80/20, v/v) since it provided the highest
223 number of metabolites extracted with high intensity as can be seen in Fig. 1(iii).

224 225 *3.2. CE-UV analysis of soybean metabolites.*

226
227 The objective in this part of the work was to obtain a BGE compatible with the
228 subsequent ESI-MS analysis and able to provide fast separation with high resolution
229 and sensitivity. The effect of different separation parameters on resolution, sensitivity,
230 analysis time, and peak shape was studied using a methanol/water (80/20, v/v) extract
231 from commercial soybean. Preliminary experiments were carried out using CE with UV
232 detection in order to find a suitable background electrolyte (BGE) compatible with CE-
233 ESI-MS [45,46]. For this reason, in this work only volatile BGEs were tested at
234 different pH values and ionic strengths. Initially, the conditions tested were type,
235 concentration and pH of buffer. First, ammonium hydrogencarbonate and ammonium
236 acetate at 100 mM and pH 10 were tested. In general the profiles obtained using
237 carbonate-containing BGEs were better than the obtained with acetate. Finally
238 ammonium hydrogencarbonate was selected because of the short analysis time provided
239 by this BGE (data not shown).

240 Next, the effect of BGEs at different pH values (8, 9 and 10) adjusted by adding
241 ammonium hydroxide was studied. A pH value of 9 was selected as optimum in term of

242 efficiency, resolution and analysis speed. The effect of the BGE ionic strength was next
243 studied testing concentrations of 25, 50 and 100 mM. The best results were obtained
244 with 50 and 100 mM of ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9 observing slightly better
245 resolution with 100 mM while, as expected, the analysis time was shorter with 50 mM.
246 To improve the resolution between peaks, different percentages of organic solvent
247 (acetonitrile, ACN) were added to the two buffers (50 and 100 mM ammonium
248 hydrogencarbonate). The best results in terms of peak shape and resolution were
249 obtained with the following 3 BGEs: 50 mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9, 50
250 mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9 + 20% v/v ACN, and 100 mM ammonium
251 hydrogencarbonate at pH 9. As no significant differences were found in CE-UV
252 between these three buffers, they were selected for a posterior study by CE-ESI-TOF-
253 MS choosing then the most appropriate BGE.

254 Based on these conditions different voltages: 20, 25, 28 and 30 kV were applied
255 and we found that in general a voltage of 28 kV shortened the analysis time and also
256 gave good resolution and acceptable electrical current values (around 35 μ A with the
257 buffer 50 mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate, 28 μ A with 50 mM ammonium
258 hydrogencarbonate + 20% v/v ACN and 65 μ A with 100 mM ammonium
259 hydrogencarbonate). The injection were made at the anodic end using N₂ pressure of
260 3570 Pa for 3, 5, 10 and 15 s, selecting 10 s as optimum injection in terms of sensitivity,
261 resolution and stability of the separation.

262 The repeatability of the optimised CE-UV method, using 50 mM ammonium
263 hydrogencarbonate at pH 9 as BGE, was then evaluated by carrying out three replicate
264 determinations with the same sample and with three different extracts and was
265 expressed by the relative standard deviation (RSD) for the migration time and for the
266 peak area. The RSDs of analysis time and peak area were determined for three of the
267 peaks present in the extracts. The results can be observed in Table 1 showing that the
268 procedure is repeatable.

269

270 3.3. Optimization of ESI-MS parameters

271

272 In order to select the BGE most compatible with CE-ESI-TOF-MS the three
273 mentioned buffers were tested using as sheath liquid isopropanol/water (50/50, v/v) +
274 0.1% v/v ammonium hydroxide (Fig. 2). The best results in terms of sensitivity were
275 obtained with 50 mM of ammonium hydrogencarbonate (Figure 2(i)). Therefore, these
276 conditions were chosen for the subsequent ESI optimization.

277

278 Sheath liquid composition, sheath liquid flow rate, nebulizer pressure, dry gas
279 flow rate and ESI chamber temperature were then optimized, selecting the MS intensity
280 of several peaks as optimization criterion. The choice of these variables represented a
281 compromise between maintaining efficient and well-resolved electrophoretic separation
282 and improving ionisation performance. Sheath-liquid isopropanol/water (50/50) was
283 tested together with different quantities (0.1 and 0.5% v/v) of TEA and ammonium
284 hydroxide trying to improve the ionisation yield. The highest MS signal was achieved
285 using a sheath-liquid containing 0.1% v/v ammonium hydroxide. Therefore, the sheath
286 liquid selected was composed of water-2-propanol (50/50, v/v) and 0.1% v/v
287 ammonium hydroxide. As optimum sheath liquid flow a value of 0.24 ml/h was selected
288 because lower flows reduced the ionization yield due to the instability of the spray,
289 while at higher flows dilution of the electrophoretic bands emerging from the capillary
290 was too high and the intensity of the MS signal for these compounds was reduced. The
other ESI parameters were chosen according to the sheath liquid flow of 0.24 ml/h and

291 the most suitable ones were: nebulizer pressure of 0.4 bar, dry gas flow equal to 4 l/min
292 and dry gas temperature 180°C.

293 In summary, the best results were obtained by using the following CE-ESI-MS
294 conditions: the running buffer was 50 mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9,
295 voltage 28 kV and 10 s of hydrodynamic injection at 3570 Pa. The sheath liquid
296 consisted of water-2-propanol (50/50, v/v) with 0.1% v/v ammonium hydroxide
297 pumped at 0.24 mL/h, used together with a nebulizer gas pressure at 0.4 bar and a dry
298 gas flow rate of 4 l/min at 180°C. With these optimum conditions the electric current
299 was around 35 μ A.

300 Fig. 3 shows the CE-MS base peak electropherogram of an extract of
301 commercial soybean as well as the extracted ion electropherograms (in migration order)
302 obtained under optimum CE-ESI-TOF-MS conditions. As can be seen, under these
303 conditions a large number of metabolites could be detected.

304

305 *3.4. Identification of compounds*

306

307 The identification of the majority of metabolites can be performed by a careful
308 interpretation of the mass spectra combined with the aid of their electrophoretic
309 mobility. The assignment was later confirmed by soybean composition and metabolic
310 pathways found in literature. The compounds tentatively identified are summarized in
311 Table 2, including experimental m/z values, fragments detected, the error and sigma
312 value (comparison of the theoretical with the measured isotope pattern) a list of possible
313 compounds and references about these including soybean pathways.

314 A reduced number of possible elemental compositions are obtained from the
315 accurate mass of the suspected peak combined with the correct determination of the
316 isotopic pattern applying ESI-TOF-MS analyzer. These elemental compositions can
317 then be matched against available databases using the deduced molecular formula as a
318 search criterion [47,48].

319 Additional proves that corroborate the adequacy of the compounds given in
320 Table 2 can be found from the electrophoretic mobility of these compounds. The total
321 migration time for highly charged small molecules is longer than that for molecules of
322 smaller charge and greater size [49].

323 The first group of peaks migrated very close to the EOF and most of them were
324 identified as aminoacids (essential aminoacids present in soybean and others produced
325 via secondary metabolism [50]) as e.g., proline, 4-hydroxy-L-threonine, leucine,
326 tyrosine, asparagine. They have a carboxylic group that at pH 9 will be fully ionized and
327 also have a primary amine susceptible to bear positive charge at that pH, giving rise to a
328 net charge near to zero that explains this behaviour.

329 The last migrating peaks (as e.g., glutamic acid, aspartic acid) correspond to
330 compounds with carboxylic groups that are totally ionized at the separation pH 9,
331 providing to the molecules the highest negative electrical charge/size ratio, the lowest
332 apparent electrophoretic mobility and therefore high migration time.

333 Major isoflavones previously observed in several studies [41, 42, 44] were also
334 detected in the present work. Soybean was revealed to be more abundant in malonyl
335 derivatives of genistin and daidzin, followed by genistin, daidzin and their aglicones
336 (genistein and daidzein). In spite of their abundance in soybean seeds, malonyl forms
337 are thermally unstable and are easily converted into their corresponding glycosides
338 forms.

339 Interestingly, the migration order of the isoflavones, previously studied in
340 literature [41, 42], is also in good agreement with our results. Thus, the glycosides

341 (daidzin and genistin) were detected earlier because of their higher molecular weights;
342 then the malonyl derivatives migrated due to increased electrophoretic mobility with the
343 introduction of a negative charge (malonate) to the sugar that overcompensate the
344 increase in molecular mass. The smaller aglycone molecules with higher mobility
345 toward the anode and against the EOF were detected latest. In all cases daidzein was
346 detected before genistein because of the extra hydroxyl group of genistein [51].

347 The glycosides and their malonyl derivatives also contain the [M-H] ions
348 corresponding to their aglicones forms produced in the electrospray (ESI-TOF) so, we
349 can observe in the extracted ion electropherograms (EIEs) of daidzein (253,049) and
350 genistein (269,044) three peaks: first two correspond to the fragments of the glycosides
351 and malonyl derivatives and the last one is the aglycon.

352 Although these isoflavones are the predominant flavonoids in soybean seeds,
353 other flavonoids have been tentatively identified in this work since flavonoids are one of
354 the largest and most widespread groups of plant secondary metabolites [52]. The first
355 two phenolic compounds tentatively identified as dihydro tetramethoxyflavone
356 triglucoside and medicarpin 3-O-glucoside showed peaks migrating near the EOF, in
357 good agreement with its low ionizable character. Daidzin and genistin migrated later
358 than the EOF due to a partial ionization of the free -OH groups at the basic running
359 buffer. Other flavonoids identified were: taxifolin 3- ramoside, naringenin
360 7- glucoside, 6-methoxytaxifolin and formononetin.

361 Besides it is very common to find in plant extracts flavonoid glycosided acylated
362 with acids such as malonic, acetic, coumaric etc [53,54] as e.g., liquiritigenin
363 6- coumarylglucoside, tentatively identified in soybean extract.

364 Small traces of other flavonoids in soybean extract were tentatively identified as:
365 Kushenol M, Sophora-iso-flavanone D, Exiguaflavanone and Kushenol B that contain
366 prenyl, geranyl, lavandulyl and similar groups. These results are in good agreement with
367 the data found in the literature about plants belonging to the family of Fabacea [55,56]
368 in which some isoflavones with prenyl groups or further O-heterocyclic rings were
369 detected. Nevertheless, the high sigma and error values found for these compounds have
370 to be also considered (see Table 2).

371 It was also possible to study other compounds present in this fraction of the
372 soybean. Among them we found compounds from the linoleic acid metabolism as e.g.,
373 trihydroxyoctadec-11-enoic and epoxyoctadecenoic acid, other belonging to arachidonic
374 acid metabolism as e.g. 2, 3- Dinor-8-iso prostaglandin F1-alpha and dipeptides as γ -L-
375 glutamyl-L-tyrosine and γ -L-glutamyl-L-phenylalanine [57]. These and other
376 compounds are listed in Table 2.

377

378 *3.5. Comparison between conventional and transgenic soybean*

379

380 A comparison between the metabolomic profile obtained with the transgenic
381 soybean and its isogenic wild variety was next carried. As can be seen in Table 3,
382 comparing the two samples (conventional and GM soybean), certain compounds were
383 detected in both soybeans, although there were interesting differences in the intensity of
384 their signals. Thus, the GM soybean produced higher amounts of some metabolites (as
385 e.g., liquiritigenin 6-coumaroylglucoside, naringenin 7-O-glucoside and 6-
386 methoxytaxifolin), while for other metabolites (as e.g., proline, histidine, asparagine,
387 gluconic acid, and trihydroxypentanoic acid) the conventional soybean produced higher
388 amounts. However, the main qualitative difference between GM and wild soybeans was
389 found in the compound 6 tentatively identified as 4-hydroxy-L-threonine (m/z 134). Fig.
390 4 shows the comparison of the extracted ion electropherograms (EIEs) of some analytes

391 identified by CE-ESI-TOF-MS in the transgenic and conventional soybeans. Comparing
392 the results for the two samples, we could not find 4-hydroxy-L-threonine in the
393 electropherogram obtained with transgenic soybean. We have represented this
394 compound with an asterisk and have compared it with other peaks that as can be seen
395 are unchanged what eliminates any possible analytical artifact. Before this compound
396 can be assigned as a possible indicator of this genetic modification, a large number of
397 samples should be analyzed.

398 On the basis of obtained data, some biochemical considerations can be drawn.
399 By comparing conventional and GM metabolite profiles a different expression of three
400 free amino acids (i.e. proline, histidine and asparagine) and of one amino acid derivative
401 (i.e. 4-hydroxy-L-threonine) was observed. Although proline, asparagine and threonine
402 are biosynthesized in different anabolic pathways (glutamine-proline, alanine-
403 asparagine and threonine-methionine pathways, respectively), they are interconnected
404 sharing a common precursor. The common precursor of proline and asparagine is the
405 glutamic acid, while the precursor of threonine is the aspartic acid [5]. It is to underline
406 that glyphosate resistant soybean expresses both endogenous and transgenic EPSPS
407 [6,7]. As a consequence considering that EPSPS is a key enzyme of shikimate pathway,
408 it is plausible that the synthesis of aromatic amino acids (phenylalanine, tyrosine,
409 tryptophan) may be differently regulated in GM soybean and corresponding isogenic
410 line. The different allosteric properties of eukaryote (endogenous soybean enzyme) and
411 prokaryote (*A. tumefaciens* enzyme) EPSPS may be the basis of different biosynthetic
412 regulatory systems. The presumable different regulation of shikimate pathways can
413 explain the higher relative content of liquiritigenin, naringenin and taxifolin derivatives
414 observed in GM soybean. In fact, these three compounds share common precursors: the
415 aromatic amino acids phenylalanine and tyrosine for the flavanones naringenin and
416 liquiritigenin, and narigenin for the majority of flavonoids (including the flavonol
417 taxifolin) [58]. Further studies are in progress in order to confirm at transcriptional level
418 the observed metabolomic differences between GM and conventional soybean.

419

420 **4. Conclusions**

421

422 In the present work, a complete analytical method (including an extraction
423 protocol, CE-ESI-TOF-MS analysis and data evaluation) has been developed to
424 comparatively study the metabolic profile of conventional and GM soybean. This
425 method allows the tentative identification of more than forty compounds, including,
426 isoflavones, aminoacids, carboxylic acids, peptides and other analytes. The results show
427 that some of the detected metabolites do not change, while other show significant
428 quantitative differences in their intensities in the conventional and GM soybean. A
429 compound tentatively identified as 4-hydroxy-L-threonine seems to disappear in the
430 transgenic soybean compared to its parental non-transgenic line.

431

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434 **Figure legends**

435

436 Fig. 1. CE-UV electropherograms of soybean extracts obtained using the following
437 solvents: (i) methanol; (ii) methanol/water, 90/10; (iii) methanol/water, 80/20; (iv)
438 methanol/water, 60/40; (v) ethanol, (vi) ethanol/water, 90/10; (vii) ethanol/water, 80/20;
439 (viii) ethanol/water, 60/40; (ix) acetonitrile; (x) acetonitrile/water, 70/30; (xi) ethyl
440 acetate. All the solvents were compared under the same initial conditions: fused-silica
441 capillary with 50 μm i.d., 375 μm o.d., 90 cm total length, running buffer 100 mM
442 ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9 + 5% v/v acetonitrile, voltage: 28 kV, 5 s
443 injection time, electrophoretic current 80 μA . Detection wavelength: 200 nm.

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445 Fig. 2. CE-TOF-MS electropherograms using as BGE: (i) 50mM ammonium
446 hydrogencarbonate, (ii) 50mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate +20% v/v ACN, (iii)
447 100mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate. The rest of CE-ESI-MS conditions were:
448 voltage: 28 kV; injection time: 10 s; sheath liquid: 2-propanol/water 50:50 (v/v)
449 containing 0.1% v/v ammonium hydroxide, flow rate 0.24 mL/h, drying gas: 4 l/min at
450 180°C, nebulising gas pressure: 4 bar. MS analyses were carried out using negative
451 polarity. MS scan 50-1000 m/z.

452

453 Fig. 3. CE-TOF-MS Base peak electropherogram (BPE) of commercial soybean, using
454 the optimal conditions and CE-TOF-MS extracted ion electropherograms (EIEs) of the
455 detected compounds. CE-MS conditions: Buffer: 50 mM ammonium
456 hydrogencarbonate at pH 9. Voltage: 28 kV. Injection time: 10 s. Sheath liquid: 2-
457 propanol/water 50:50 (v/v) containing 0.1% v/v ammonium hydroxide, flow rate 0.24
458 mL/h. Drying gas: 4 l/min at 180°C. Nebulising gas pressure: 4 bar. Electrophoretic
459 current 35 μA . MS analyses were carried out using negative polarity. MS scan 50-1000
460 m/z.

461

462 Fig. 4. Comparison of the CE-TOF-MS extracted ions electropherograms (EIEs) of
463 some metabolites found in conventional and transgenic soybean. * compound that
464 changes; 1, 2, 11, 12, 17 unmodified compounds. Peak numbers correspond to the
465 compounds identified in Table 2. All the conditions as in Fig. 3.

466

467 **Table 1.** Mean, standard deviation (SD) and relative standard deviation (RSD) of three
 468 peaks in three consecutive injections of the same extract and with three different
 469 extracts.
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	Three different injections		Three different extracts	
	Peak area	Analysis time	Peak area	Analysis time
Mean				
Peak 1	0.151	6.63	0.130	6.61
Peak 2	0.130	10.60	0.111	10.59
Peak 3	0.560	12.01	0.490	11.96
SD				
Peak 1	0.0170	0.019	0.0191	0.035
Peak 2	0.0102	0.044	0.0182	0.076
Peak 3	0.0361	0.067	0.0804	0.100
RSD (%)				
Peak 1	11.3	0.29	14.6	0.53
Peak 2	7.88	0.42	16.4	0.72
Peak 3	6.45	0.56	16.4	0.84

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474**Table 2.** Metabolites detected by CE-ESI-TOF-MS in a soybean extract.

	Mass	Migration time (min)	Fragments	Molecular formula	Error (ppm)	Sigma	Possible compounds	Pathways and references
1	173.1048	8.431	131.0822	C6H13N4O2	2.4	0.0579	Arginine	Arginine and proline metabolism [50]
2	845.2770	9.686	683.2248/665.2139/ 503.1617/341.1100	C37H49O22	-5.9	0.2174	Dihydro tetramethoxyflavone triglucoside	
3	431.1429	9.787		C22H23O9	-8.9	0.1435	Medicarpin 3-O-glucoside	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis
4	114.0557	9.937		C5H8NO2	3.1	0.0420	Proline	Arginine and proline metabolism [50]
5	415.1056	10.004	253.0542	C21H19O9	-5.3	0.0269	Daidzein 7-O-glucoside (daidzin)	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
6	134.0472	10.054		C4H8NO4	-9.4	0.0290	4-Hydroxy-L-threonine	Vitamin B6 metabolism
7	431.0983	10.071	269.0455	C21H19O10	0.1	0.0335	Genistein 7-O-glucoside (genistin)	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
8	130.0876	10.221		C6H12NO2	-1.8	0.0057	Leucine	Valine, leucine and isoleucine degradation [50]
9	203.0831	10.272		C11H11N2O2	-2.5	0.0068	Tryptophan	Tryptophan metabolism [50]
10	131.0826	10.339		C5H11N2O2	-0.4	0.0449	2,5-Diaminopentanoic acid(ornithine)	Urea cycle and metabolism of amino groups
11	173.0937	10.355		C7H13N2O3	-3.5	0.0498	N-Acetylornithine	Urea cycle and metabolism of amino groups
12	180.0666	10.489		C9H10NO3	0.2	0.0600	Tyrosine	Tyrosine metabolism [50]
13	154.0627	10.539		C6H8N3O2	-3.5	0.0549	Histidine	Histidine metabolism [50]
14	164.0719	10.573		C9H10NO2	-1.6	0.0597	Phenylalanine	Phenylalanine metabolism [50]
15	131.0467	10.890		C4H7N2O3	-4.0	0.0372	Asparagine	Alanine and aspartate metabolism [50]
16	663.2668	12.028		C33H43O14	-1.4	0.1898	C33H43O14	
17	563.1622	12.429		C30H27O11	-11.2	0.1703	Liquiritigenin 6-coumarylglucoside	Chalcone biosynthesis (isoflavone precursor)
18	443.1920	12.596		C21H31O10	0.7	0.1384	C21H31O10	
19	329.2343	12.847		C18H33O5	-2.9	0.1169	Trihydroxyoctadec-11-enoic acid	Linoleic acid metabolism
20	449.1087	12.864		C21H21O11	-1.6	0.1378	Taxifolin 3-rhamnoside	Flavonol biosynthesis
21	327.2160	12.880		C18H31O5	5.3	0.4330	2,3-Dinor-8-iso prostaglandin F1alpha	Arachidonic acid metabolism
22	433.1132	12.897	457.1149/253.0504	C21H21O10	4.2	0.1374	Naringenin 7-O-glucoside	Chalcone biosynthesis (isoflavone precursor)
23	501.1062	12.998	473.1084/269.0452	C24H21O12	2.8	0.2790	Daidzein 7-O- malonylglucoside	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
24	517.1028	13.148		C24H21O13	-0.3	0.1370	Genistein 7-O-malonylglucoside	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
25	295.2278	13.215		C18H31O3	0.2	0.1160	Epoxyoctadecenoic acid	Linoleic acid metabolism
26	333.0605	13.516		C16H13O8	3.1	0.1041	6-Methoxytaxifolin	Flavonol biosynthesis
27	521.2661	13.767		C31H37O7	-12.3	0.1748	Kushenol M	Flavanone biosynthesis
28	491.2523	13.834		C30H35O6	-7.1	0.1686	Sophora-iso- flavanone D	Flavanone biosynthesis
29	519.2488	13.867		C31H35O7	-9.3	0.1747	Exiguaflavanone D	Flavanone biosynthesis
30	505.2527	13.901		C31H37O6	13.6	0.1744	Kushenol B	Flavanone biosynthesis
31	267.0675	14.218		C16H11O4	4.4	0.0845	Formononetin	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis
32	253.0494	14.671		C15H9O4	4.9	0.0959	Daidzein	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
33	269.0446	14.855	128.0340	C15H9O5	3.4	0.0963	Genistein	Isoflavonoid biosynthesis [41,42,44]
34	309.1077	15.290		C14H17N2O6	4.7	0.0143	γ- L- Glutamyl-L- tyrosine	Dipeptide (carboxypeptide) biosynthesis [57]
35	293.1136	15.491		C14H17N2O5	2.5	0.0187	γ-L-Glutamyl-L-phenylalanine	Dipeptide (carboxypeptide) biosynthesis [57]
36	195.0506	15.809		C6H11O7	2.4	0.0408	Gluconic acid (L-gluconate)	Pentose phosphate pathway
37	179.0556	15.959	128.0732	C6H11O6	2.9	0.0404	Fuconate	Fructose and mannose metabolism
38	172.0613	16.277	146.0458	C7H10NO4	1.1	0.0478	N-Acetyl-L-glutamate 5-semialdehyde	Urea cycle and metabolism of amino groups
39	176.0555	16.929		C6H10NO5	5.5	0.0420	4-Hydroxy-4-methyl glutamate	Glutamate metabolism
40	319.0822	16.962		C16H15O7	0.3	0.1038	4-Coumaroylshikimate	Phenylpropanoid biosynthesis
41	149.0449	17.079		C5H9O5	4.4	0.0336	Trihydroxypentanoic acid	Alkyl carboxylic acid biosynthesis
42	165.0396	17.197	128.0340	C5H9O6	5.3	0.0341	Tetrahydroxypentanoic acid (L-xylonate)	Pentose and glucuronate interconversion
43	146.0454	17.882		C5H8NO4	3.6	0.0352	Glutamic acid	Glutamate metabolism [50]
44	135.0296	18.016		C4H7O5	2.3	0.0273	Trihydroxybutanoate (threonate)	Ascorbate and aldarate metabolism
45	132.0298	18.718		C4H6NO4	3.0	0.0289	Aspartic acid	Alanine and aspartate metabolism [50]

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Table 3. Metabolites detected by CE-TOF-MS in conventional and GM soybeans

	Mass	Possible compounds	Conventional	GM
1	173.1048	Arginine	YES	YES
2	845.2770	Dihydro tetramethoxyflavone triglucoside	YES	YES
3	431.1429	Medicarpin 3-O-glucoside	YES	YES
4	114.0557	Proline	YES*	YES
5	415.1056	Daidzein 7-O-glucoside (daidzin)	YES	YES
6	134.0472	4-Hydroxy-L-threonine	YES	NO
7	431.0983	Genistein 7-O-glucoside (genistin)	YES	YES
8	130.0876	Leucine	YES	YES
9	203.0831	Tryptophan	YES	YES
10	131.0826	2,5-Diaminopentanoic acid(ornithine)	YES	YES
11	173.0937	N-Acetylmethionine	YES	YES
12	180.0666	Tyrosine	YES	YES
13	154.0627	Histidine	YES*	YES
14	164.0719	Phenylalanine	YES	YES
15	131.0467	Asparagine	YES*	YES
16	663.2668	C33H43O14	YES	YES
17	563.1622	Liquiritigenin 6-coumaroylglucoside	YES	YES ^{&}
18	443.1920	C21H31O10	YES	YES
19	329.2343	Trihydroxyoctadec-11-enoic acid	YES	YES
20	449.1087	Taxifolin 3-rhamnoside	YES	YES
21	327.2160	2,3-Dinor-8-iso prostaglandin F1alpha	YES	YES
22	433.1132	Naringenin 7-O-glucoside	YES	YES ^{&}
23	501.1062	Daidzein 7-O- malonylglucoside	YES	YES
24	517.1028	Genistein 7-O-malonylglucoside	YES	YES
25	295.2278	Epoxyoctadecenoic acid	YES	YES
26	333.0605	6-Methoxytaxifolin	YES	YES ^{&}
27	521.2661	Kushenol M	YES	YES
28	491.2523	Sophora-iso- flavanone D	YES	YES
29	519.2488	Exiguaflavanone D	YES	YES
30	505.2527	Kushenol B	YES	YES
31	267.0675	Formononetin	YES	YES
32	253.0494	Daidzein	YES	YES
33	269.0446	Genistein	YES	YES
34	309.1077	γ- L- Glutamyl- L- tyrosine	YES	YES
35	293.1136	γ- L- Glutamyl- L- phenylalanine	YES	YES
36	195.0506	Gluconic acid (L-gluconate)	YES*	YES
37	179.0556	Fuconate	YES	YES
38	172.0613	N-Acetyl-L- glutamate 5-semialdehyde	YES	YES
39	176.0555	4-Hydroxy-4-methyl glutamate	YES	YES
40	319.0822	4-Coumaroylshikimate	YES	YES
41	149.0449	Trihydroxypentanoic acid	YES*	YES
42	165.0396	Tetrahydroxypentanoic acid (L-xylonate)	YES	YES
43	146.0454	Glutamic acid	YES	YES
44	135.0296	Trihydroxybutanoate (threonate)	YES	YES
45	132.0298	Aspartic acid	YES	YES

* means peak area of the compound is significantly higher ($p > 0.95$) in conventional soybean than in transgenic soybean;

& means peak area of the compound is significantly higher ($p > 0.95$) in transgenic soybean than in conventional soybean.

521 **Fig. 1.** CE-UV electropherograms of soybean extracts obtained using the following
522 solvents: (i) methanol; (ii) methanol/water, 90/10; (iii) methanol/water, 80/20; (iv)
523 methanol/water, 60/40; (v) ethanol, (vi) ethanol/water, 90/10; (vii) ethanol/water, 80/20;
524 (viii) ethanol/water, 60/40; (ix) acetonitrile; (x) acetonitrile/water, 70/30; (xi) ethyl
525 acetate. All the solvents were compared under the same initial conditions: fused-silica
526 capillary with 50_μm I.D., 375_μm O.D., 90cm total length, running buffer 100mM
527 ammonium hydrogencarbonate at pH 9 + 5% (v/v) acetonitrile, voltage: 28 kV, 5 s
528 injection time, electrical current 80_μA. Detection wavelength: 200 nm.
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537 **Fig. 2.** CE-TOF-MS electropherograms using as BGE: (i) 50mM ammonium
538 hydrogencarbonate, (ii) 50mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate + 20% (v/v) ACN, (iii)
539 100mM ammonium hydrogencarbonate. The rest of CE-ESI-MS conditions were:
540 voltage: 28 kV; injection time: 10 s; sheath liquid: 2-propanol/water 50:50 (v/v)
541 containing 0.1% (v/v) ammonium hydroxide, flow rate 0.24mL/h, drying gas: 4 L/min
542 at 180 °C, nebulizing gas pressure: 4 bar. MS analyses were carried out using negative
543 polarity. MS scan 50–1000m/z
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549 **Figure 3.** CE-TOF-MS base peak electropherogram (BPE) of commercial soybean,
550 using the optimal conditions and CE-TOF-MS extracted ion electropherograms (EIEs)
551 of the detected compounds. CE-MS conditions: Buffer: 50mM ammonium
552 hydrogencarbonate at pH 9. Voltage: 28 kV. Injection time: 10 s. Sheath liquid: 2-
553 propanol/water 50:50 (v/v) containing 0.1% (v/v) ammonium hydroxide, flowrate
554 0.24mL/h. Drying gas: 4 L/min at 180 °C. Nebulizing gas pressure: 4 bar. Electrical
555 current 35_A. MS analyses were carried out using negative polarity. MS scan 50–
556 1000m/z.
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563 **Figure 4.** Comparison of the CE-TOF-MS extracted ions electropherograms (EIEs) of
564 some metabolites found in conventional and transgenic soybean. (*) compound that
565 changes; 1, 2, 11, 12, 17 unmodified compounds. Peak numbers correspond to the
566 compounds identified in Table 2. Conditions as in Fig. 3.
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